

Generalized Approximators and Approximators for Exponential Calculus

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Abstract

In this paper we will be introducing the notion of tangents lines being linear approximators to a curve. We generalize this notion to Multiplicative Calculus to show that we get in analogy a tangent exponential curve or more precisely we get a multiplicative approximator. We generalize this to give a recursive pattern for generating higher approximators and find an analogy in Exponential Calculus

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1 Introduction

The first thing we must do is we must define all the required differential operators . Let us say our ordinary calculus is a special case of this generalization called Additive Calculus.

$$D_{Add} = \frac{d}{dx} \quad (1)$$

Similarly we define for Multiplicative Calculus:

$$D_{Mult} = e^{\frac{d}{dx}} \quad (2)$$

The analogous notion for Exponential Calculus is not clear. But the respective "Tangent curves" are still well defined via simple analytic reasoning

let T_A be the tangent line or linear approximator then T_M is the multiplicative approximator and T_E is the exponential approximator

1.1 Approximator Curves

So the Tangent line to a curve $f(x)$ is given by

$$T_A = f'(a) \cdot (x - a) + f(a) \quad (3)$$

Similarly the Multiplicative Approximator to a curve $f(x)$ is given by

$$T_M = f'(a)^{(x-a)} \cdot f(a) \quad (4)$$

Note: We prefer "Approximator" over "Tangent" So the Tangent line to a curve $f(x)$ is given by

$$T_E = ({}^{(x-a)}f'(a))^{f(a)} \quad (5)$$

where ${}^a b$ is b exponentiated a times

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Figure 1: All the approximators graphed

2 Calculating T_E without direct tetration

2.1 Tetrating without Tetration

$$T_E = ((x - a)f'(a)) f(a)$$

Now,

$$x z = e^{z^{x-1} + z^{x-2} \int_0^x \ln t dt}$$

$$(x-a) z = e^{z^{x-a-1} + z^{x-a-2} \int_0^x \ln t dt}$$

$$z = f'(a)$$

$$T_E = e^{[f(a)f'(a)^{(x-a-1)} + f(a)f'(a)^{x-a-2} \int_0^{x-a} \ln(t) dt]}$$

Take a special case,

Let $f(x) = x^2 \Rightarrow f'(x) = 2x$

$$f(a) = a^2, \quad f'(a) = 2a$$

$$T_A = 2a(x - a) + a^2$$

$$T_m = (2a)^{(x-a)} \cdot a^2$$

$$T_E = e^{[a^2(2a)^{(x-a-1)} + a^2(2a)^{x-a-2} \int_0^{x-a} \ln(t) dt]}$$

When graphed side by side the tangents look like this

Acknowledgements

This unnumbered section should be blank when submitting your paper. After review, you may include lists of people and organizations who supported the work.

A First Appendix Section

Appendix sections should be ordered by letters rather than numbers, and their contents do not count towards the paper's length limit. Appendix sections may also contain additional tables and figures.